

Canterbury Tales Project Newsletter 2 (August 1994).

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Editorial

The year since publication of our first newsletter, in August 1993, has seen many developments in the Project, in the areas of publication, funding, collaboration with other scholars, and progress towards release of the first Project CD-ROMs. In December 1993 we published the first volume of our *Occasional Papers* series. On the back page of this newsletter, we outline the contents of this first volume and report plans for the second volume, for which we have already received several contributions.

We have received our first major funding, firstly from the University of Sheffield and secondly from the British Academy. The first tranche of funding, from the University of Sheffield, made it possible for us to employ two transcribers in Sheffield for a year from 1st February 1994. The second tranche of funding, from the British Academy, will allow us to employ these two transcribers for a second year, beginning 1st February 1995. The article 'The Transcriptions', outlines the work being done by these two transcribers, Estelle Stubbs and Michael Pidd. Their work is being supplemented by that of graduate students supervised by our Director, Norman Blake. Between these, we hope to have complete transcriptions of the full text of at least six manuscripts of the *Canterbury Tales* by the end of January 1996.

In the preface to the first volume of the *Occasional Papers* we remark that co-operation is essential to the success of the Project. One of the most pleasing features of the last year has been the forging of fruitful collaborations with other scholars. Dan Mosser, of Virginia Polytechnic, will provide manuscript descriptions to be published on the project CD-ROMs. These are described further in the article 'The Manuscript Descriptions'. Stephen Partridge, of the University of British Columbia is making available his transcripts of the glosses in the manuscripts, and we will be publishing these alongside our transcripts of the text of the manuscripts. Paul Thomas of Brigham Young University is taking responsibility for transcription of all the text of all the manuscripts of the Nun's Priest's Tale; see further the article 'The Transcriptions'. Elizabeth Solopova (who continues to work on the transcription) and Beverley Kennedy are linked with the project as Research Associates, giving them access to Project materials in advance of their publication; articles by these are to appear in the second *Occasional Papers* volume. We have also forged links with the Chaucer Heritage Trust, and the article 'The Chaucer Heritage Trust' introduces the work of this organization.

Publication by Cambridge University Press of the first Project CD-ROM, covering the Wife of Bath's Prologue, is scheduled for mid-April 1995. The article 'The CD-ROMs' outlines the features currently planned for this, and previews what we intend for the next CD-ROMs following.

We have become increasingly aware of the deficiencies in all the current systems of dividing and lineating the *Canterbury Tales*. The longest article in this newsletter, 'The New Lineation', describes the new system of lineation devised for the Project by Norman Blake. We particularly invite comments on this system: it will be comparatively easy to make changes in this scheme before we publish any CD-ROMs, and progressively more difficult thereafter.

The Transcriptions

The more people we have transcribing manuscripts, the quicker we can proceed with this Project. We now have transcribers working in three different countries. In Sheffield, two transcribers, Michael Pidd and Estelle Stubbs, have each been funded by the University of Sheffield for a year from February 1994 to work half-time on transcription. Since February they have completed transcription and a first check of the whole text of Ellesmere and Hengwrt, and also done a final check of many of the Wife of Bath's Prologue transcripts. They will next tackle Corpus Christi Oxford MS 198 (Cp), and we now have further funding from the British Academy for them to continue until February 1996. Also in Sheffield, Linda Cross and Claire Thomson will

be transcribing Harleian 7334 (Ha4) and Lansdowne 851 (Ld) respectively, as part of their graduate dissertations under the direction of Norman Blake.

At Brigham Young University, Utah, Paul Thomas has undertaken to supervise transcription of all the manuscripts of the Nun's Priest's Tale and associated links. In Moscow, Russia, Elizabeth Solopova is carrying out the second check of the Sheffield transcripts of El and Hg, and will also check the Brigham Young transcripts. If funding permits, she may also supervise the transcription of another part of the Tales in all the manuscripts (perhaps, the General Prologue). We congratulate Elizabeth on the successful completion of her Oxford doctoral dissertation on Middle English prosody.

Management of a transcription spread so widely as this is demanding, and only conceivable with the magic of electronic mail. The reward is the shortening of the task by the application of many hands. Our aim is to have the full text of six complete manuscripts and of two tale units in all the manuscripts transcribed and fully checked by the end of 1995. This will amount to around 15% of our whole task, on course for the goal of completion of the whole project within the ten-year period we have set ourselves.

The CD-ROMs

The next newsletter will contain a full description of the first project CD-ROM covering the Wife of Bath's Prologue, scheduled for release by Cambridge University Press in April 1995. The details of its contents are not yet fully decided. It will contain transcripts of all 58 manuscripts and pre-1500 printed editions of the WBP. It will also contain digital images of all pages of all manuscripts containing this text, with the possible exception of a few manuscripts (no more than three) for which we are still negotiating permissions. It will also contain several collations, considerable ancillary materials (including articles drawn from the Occasional Papers volumes).

We are particularly pleased that we will be able to include on this first CD-ROM brief (500 to 3000 word) descriptions prepared by Dan Mosser of each witness containing the , and transcripts of all the glosses in all the manuscripts of the WBP, prepared by Stephen Partridge. Both these are intended as first stages towards, respectively, a completely new description of the early witnesses to the *Canterbury Tales* (so superceding Manly and Rickert Volume I) and a complete edition of all the glosses in all the witnesses. The Project is most fortunate in being able to benefit from the years of work done by Mosser and Partridge. This will greatly enhance the value of all we do.

We are already planning the next CD-ROMs. We will have completed transcription of several important manuscripts, in full, in the next year. It is technically possible to include a digital image record of a whole manuscript on a CD-ROM. Our experiments have shown that colour digital photography direct from the manuscripts, creating 24 bit colour images at 300 dpi resolution, give quality comparable to that of the best printed facsimiles. Using JPEG compression, some five hundred such images may be accommodated on a single CD-ROM: enough for a full manuscript. We expect that the next one or two CD-ROMs after the Wife of Bath's Prologue will be single-manuscript CD-ROMs, containing our transcription and a full digital photographic record of one manuscript.

The New Lineation

As readers of this Newsletter are aware, the Canterbury Tales Project aims to transcribe into computer form every line found in all fifteenth-century witnesses of the poem. This naturally means having a lineation which enables the computer to recognise the same line in any manuscript and which makes sure that every line has a number which is different from any other line. At present there are three major systems in use, though two of these are not far apart. These two are the systems based on the ten fragments/groups isolated by Furnivall in the nineteenth century. Either the ten fragments/groups are identified by the Roman numerals from I to X following the Furnivall order, or following the Bradshaw shift which places Fragment VII after Fragment II and amalgamates them as a single group, they are identified by the first nine capital letters of the alphabet from A to I (with Fragments II and VII sharing the letter B). The order of the fragments in the latter numbering system is different from that in the former one. These two systems are usually found side by side, since the lines included in any fragment/group are the same whether an editor is using one system or the other. They are used, for example, in *The Riverside Chaucer* (1987) and are commonly found in most critical works. The third system is that found in Blake's edition of the poem based on the Hengwrt manuscript (1980) and is based

on the sectional grouping of the tales found in Hg. Since there are twelve sections there, the numbering in this system runs in Arabic numerals from 1 to 12. This system has not been widely adopted.

When we came to start transcription on the Wife of Bath's Prologue we followed the traditional fragment numeration, but we soon ran into difficulties. Those who have tried to use the Manly-Rickert edition of the poem (1940) know how difficult it can be, when using their apparatus criticus, to find out precisely what a given manuscript contains at any particular point. They themselves evidently toyed with the idea of developing a new lineation, but eventually decided against it. But their purpose was to produce an edition of what they considered the original master copy of the poem contained and so they were less concerned with all those parts of the poem which they considered spurious because they were not in that master copy. We cannot take that view since we are recording everything from the fifteenth century, whether it turns out to be spurious or not. We do not want to prejudice what that outcome may be since we are interested at present in simply providing the data which would allow more informed discussions of the text's development. Therefore, a new system of lineation became imperative and had to be in place before the first CD-ROM was issued in 1995. The following paragraphs outline the general principles behind the new system we have adopted.

In order to compare any line or group of lines across all witnesses, the computer must recognise what lines are identical or based on the same exemplar so that it can build up an apparatus criticus. Equally it must know in what order the lines occur in the different witnesses so that the orders and what has been added or omitted can also be compared. Where one line replaces another, it must recognise that these are variants which occupy one slot though they are not the same line. Each line must have a distinctive label and that label must not only be unique but also identify the position of the line in a sequence. Quite apart from lines of text, there are numerous headings, sub-headings, quotations and marginal glosses, and all of these must have labels which allow them to be compared where necessary and their position in the text to be identified.

One aim of the project is to chart the development of the text, both the main body of the poem and the marginal annotations, over the fifteenth century. It is important not to choose a lineation system which prejudices the final outcome by implying one order or arrangement of lines is the starting point of the text's development. This is naturally difficult, for any base manuscript chosen for the lineation system could be taken to be programmatic.

Finally, it is helpful if the new system is not too far away from those currently available, but is at the same time sufficiently distinctive that it will not be confused with them.

We have tried to implement these principles in the following ways. After a consideration of the text in all witnesses, we have divided the poem into blocks which are maintained as separate entities in all the extant complete witnesses. This means that the principal units are the tales and links. Some tale units may have the prologue or epilogue included provided that the prologue or epilogue is always attached to the tale and that it does not open or close another tale. Tale units are distinguished by two capital letters referring to the teller or the tale. Thus they may reflect the teller's title: KN for Knight, PL for Ploughman; and WB for Wife of Bath, CY for Canon's Yeoman; or the name of the tale: TT for Tale of Sir Thopas, TG for Tale of Gamelyn. These abbreviations refer to whatever is included within that tale unit, which is sometimes merely the tale, but is on occasions both the tale and the prologue and/or epilogue, as is true of CY. Where confusion could arise because two pilgrims could share the same two letters (e.g. Friar and Franklin), they are distinguished usually through following traditional abbreviations: FR for Friar and FK for Franklin. Link units, on the other hand, are distinguished by L and an arbitrary number from 1 to 37. For example, L1 is the KN-MI link. These arbitrary numbers have been allocated because some links may be allocated in different witnesses to different tellers (and to refer to a link by one pair of tellers might prejudice what tales the link originally joined) and because some tales are joined together by different links in different witnesses. In the first case the link unit is treated as a single link even though it refers to different tellers, but in the second case the links are treated as separate units, although they are given continuous numbers in the sequence. Thus RE95 would refer to the ninety-fifth line of the tale unit allocated to the Reeve, and L4:1 would be the first line of link unit 4, which is the link uniting TG to CO in Ra1.

For practical purposes it is easier to start with a lineation system based on manuscript chronology, since the early manuscripts are well known and studied. To give line numbers based on a system of the lines in all the witnesses had been counted would delay a lineation system until all transcriptions were complete. The base text for lineation purposes is the earliest witness for that unit in accordance with current palaeographical dating. Although there may be discrepancies as to some datings and the order of some

manuscripts, there is a general consensus about most. Thus we take Hg as the base for much of the poem since it is widely believed to be the earliest extant manuscript, but Cp is the base for CY and TG since we consider Cp to be the earliest manuscript in which these two units are found. Where Hg fails for the end of PA and for RT because some of the manuscript is now lost (and the same applies to Cp), we use Ha4 as the base. The base text is followed scrupulously for lineation purposes except in a few minor instances. The numbering starts for each unit at 1 for the first line of the English text. Any heading for a unit is numbered 0, however long it may be. The numbering proceeds regularly to the end of that unit, with each unit being identified either by the two capitals of the tale units or L and a number for the link units. Additions in other witnesses have the base number of the preceding line, a slash and then numbering from 1. Thus WB44/1 and WB44/2 would be the first and second lines of an addition after WB44 in a given witness in what is the Wife of Bath's tale unit (which in this case also includes the prologue). If the line numbering goes from WB42 to WB45, it would signify that WB43 and WB44 were missing in that witness. A variant of a line has the base number of that line, a slash and a lower-case letter starting with a. Thus WB44/a and WB44/b would be two variants, each different from the other and from the base, of line WB44. Sub-headings within the text are recorded as additions, but marginalia and glosses over the line are treated as glosses. They are identified by gl after the line number: WB44gl would be a gloss to WB44 and WB44/2gl would be a gloss to WB44/2. Where there is more than one gloss to a line, these are distinguished by a slash and a number after the gl so that WB44gl/1 and WB44gl/2 would be two separate glosses to WB44.

It is hoped that this system is sufficiently transparent and close to previous numerations to make it readily understood by users of the computer texts. A full break-down of the units and their lineation will be provided in the second volume of the *Occasional Papers* due to be published in late 1994 or early 1995. Anyone who has any comments that they would like to make about the proposed system is invited to raise them with the project's director as soon as possible.